

3D-PRINTED SLIPCHIP FOR COLLECTION OF AQUEOUS SAMPLES WITH A SPECIFIC VOLUME

Zhiqing Xiao, Zejingqi Chen, Zitao Feng, and Weijin Guo
Shantou University, China

ABSTRACT

In this work, we developed a 3D-printed SlipChip for collecting minute aqueous samples with specific volume. Aqueous sample with certain volume is constrained in a well by slipping the top plate. Drawing out the hydrophobic film below the aqueous sample, the sample falls onto the collection membrane on the bottom plate due to gravity. We can use our chip to collect 36.3 μl aqueous sample with a variation of 2.3%, and the reliability of our chip is on par with the Eppendorf pipette. Integrated with lateral flow tests, this chip can play an important role in point-of-care diagnostics.

KEYWORDS: SlipChip, 3D printing, aqueous sample, hydrophobic film, lateral flow tests, point-of-care diagnostics

INTRODUCTION

Microsampling is a minimally invasive sampling technology gaining interest for many applications including dried blood spot sampling [1]. However, traditional methods of microsampling often make the quantitative analysis inaccurate due to variable and unknown volumes of the samples [2]. Herein, we propose a portable and compact 3D-printed SlipChip for the collection of aqueous samples with a specific volume for following bioanalysis [3]. When used for collecting aqueous samples with the same volume, the variation of our chip is on par with the Eppendorf pipette. In addition, our chip can be integrated on lateral flow tests to meter the samples tested. Fabrication of this chip by 3D printing is fast, and the cost is low, which is suitable for point-of-care diagnostics. Moreover, with improvement, our chip has the potential to be used for the collection of blood samples.

EXPERIMENTAL

Figure 1: The experimental procedures of collecting aqueous sample with a specific volume by SlipChip (a: schematic, and b: a real device), and the weight of liquid sample collected using an Eppendorf pipette, one SlipChip by an experienced user, and two SlipChips by two first-time users (c). The procedure in (b) is slightly different from that in (a), just to clearly show the sample in the well, and the scale bar in (b) is 1 cm. The dimension of the well is 3.5*3.5*2.7 mm.

The experimental steps are illustrated in Figure 1(a) and (b). The main components of SlipChip were printed by a fused deposition modeling 3D printer (Ender 3-Pro, Shenzhen Creality 3D Technology, China) using polylactic acid, and treated by hydrophobic spray (Shiduokang, Japan). This chip consists of a top slip plate, a base, a hydrophobic film, and a bottom slip plate. The hydrophobic film is a transparent film treated by hydrophobic spray (Shiduokang, Japan). We glued the collection membrane (Cobetter blood filtration membrane, PSM0180-B, China) on the bottom plate. For the experimental procedures, at first, we assembled the SlipChip, and dropped a sample droplet (DI water with 1% food dye) with excess volume into the well on the hydrophobic film. Secondly, we slipped the top plate to remove the extra sample. Thereafter, the volume of the aqueous sample was metered by the well. Fourthly, we drew out the hydrophobic film, and the aqueous sample dropped onto the collection membrane. We weighed the bottom slip plate before and after the experiment to measure the weight of aqueous sample collected.

We compared our SlipChip and Eppendorf pipette about their reliability when collecting aqueous samples with a specific volume. Firstly, we measured the weight of the aqueous sample collected by our SlipChip and calculated the volume of sample collected. Secondly, we used the Eppendorf pipette to meter the aqueous sample with the

same volume and measured its weight. For the SlipChip, we tested it by an experienced user and two first-time users. For both of SlipChip and Eppendorf pipette, we repeated every experiment for ten times.

Furthermore, we investigated the possibility by integrating the SlipChip with lateral flow tests for metering samples with a specific volume. We redesigned the bottom slip plate to accommodate a nitrocellulose lateral flow test strip, which is for quantitative detection of glucose concentration using a colorimetric enzyme assay [4]. In addition, we tested the possibility of loading different reagents on a test strip in time sequence using our chip.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our SlipChip can collect aqueous samples with a specific volume on the collection membrane. We found that the volume capacity of aqueous sample collected using the SlipChip (by an experienced user) is $36.3 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{l}$, with a variation of 2.3%. By an Eppendorf pipette with 10-100 μl as measuring range, we collected $37.1 \pm 1.0 \mu\text{l}$ aqueous sample, with a variation of 2.7%. Figure 1(c) shows the comparison of the performance of Eppendorf pipette and SlipChip (by one experienced user and two first-time users). There is no significant difference in the sample volume from Eppendorf pipette and our SlipChip. Between different SlipChip users (experience user versus first-time users), there is also no significant difference in the sample volume. Our SlipChip is printed by an entry-level 3D printer (~300 USD), and the material cost for each SlipChip is ~0.2 USD, which suits well for point-of-care diagnostics.

We integrated our SlipChip on a lateral flow test strip for glucose detection, as shown in Figure 2(a) and (b). The sample we used is pseudo urine (6 mM glucose in DI water, and with 1% yellow color dye). Using our SlipChip, pseudo urine sample with a specific volume is collected and pumped on the test strip. We can see the color change after the sample flowed through the test region (in Figure 2(b)).

We also used our SlipChip to control the sequence of reagent loading on a paper test strip, shown in Figure 2(c) and (d). From left to right in Figure 2(d), there are three types of samples (DI water with 1% food dye: blue, purple, and blue) in the wells. We loaded the blue sample in the left at first, and the purple sample in the middle after 30 s, and the blue sample in the right after ~60 s by controlling the position of the hydrophobic film. As we can see from Figure 2(d), the blue sample from the left well run in the front, followed by the purple sample in the middle well and the blue sample in the right well.

Figure 2: SlipChip integrated on lateral flow strips. (a) and (b) show a lateral flow test for glucose detection integrating our SlipChip. (c) and (d) show the sequential loading of different reagents on a strip using our SlipChip. Scale bar: 1 cm.

CONCLUSION

We developed a 3D-printed SlipChip to collect aqueous samples and proved its high reliability in collecting aqueous samples of a specific volume. We further investigated its application in lateral flow tests, which proved that it can be used to meter aqueous samples for following bioanalysis and control the loading sequence of multiple reagents.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by Shantou University (STU Scientific Research Foundation for Talents: NTF20034).

REFERENCES

- [1] Lenk et al. *Bioanalysis* 7.16 (2015): 2085-2094.
- [2] Spooner et al. *Analytical chemistry* 81.4 (2009): 1557-1563.
- [3] Du et al. *Lab on a Chip* 9.16 (2009): 2286-2292.
- [4] Guo et al. *Proceedings of IEEE NEMS 2021*: 1310-1313.

CONTACT

* Weijin Guo; guoweijin@stu.edu.cn; Zhiqing Xiao and Zejingqiu Chen contribute equally to this work.